

**17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018**

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Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
Conference President

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Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
Member of the Board CELCA

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METASTATIC RECURRENCE OF TYPICAL PULMONARY CARCINOID TREATED WITH COMBINED TREATMENT MODALITIES

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Introduction: Bronchial carcinoid tumours (BCT) are rare and uncommon group of lung tumors. They represent about 1% of all primary lung tumors. About 80% are centrally located, within the lobar and segmental bronchi. Recurrence of typical pulmonary carcinoid after complete resection is very rare (3–5%).

Case report: In 2012 a 61-year-old male presented at the Oncology Department of Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina with a history of cough and fever. Chest CT scan revealed oval mass (4x6cm) in the right lower lobe. Bronchobiospy from tumor reported adenocarcinoma. Right lower lobectomy was performed and pathological finding was typical lung carcinoid (pT2bN0Mx). At the beginning of 2016, radiologically and bronchoscopic progression of the disease has been reported. Patient received endoluminal brachytherapy. Subsequently the first line chemotherapy according to PE protocol was applied. In September 2017 electrocauterisation of tumor in the right main bronchus and APC was performed. Pathohistological finding of resection fragment was typical carcinoid of lung with low proliferative Ki index. Magnetic resonance imaging revealed an enhanced nodular lesions compatible with a liver metastases. Somatostatic receptor scintigraphy shown secondary deposits with expression SSNR in the liver and lungs (cT4N3M1c). Patient started using Somatuline Autogel. After five treatments progression of the disease has been verified. Oncology Board introduced the third line therapy with afinitor.

Conclusion: Only a small number of patients with typical carcinoid experience recurrences, with a median time to recurrence of 4 years (range, 0.8–12 years), longer than that for atypical carcinoid. Evidence supporting optimal treatment strategies for BCT is lacking but the recent publications indicate that multimodal treatment is associated with prolonged survival.

Key words: lung; typical carcinoid; brachytherapy; afinitor

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